

Mycroft1, a SherlockBench Problem-Set Where LLMs Out-Perform Random Heuristics

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1 Intro

In our previous paper [4], we introduced a benchmark where an LLM has to pro-actively investigate what a mystery function does, by repeatedly testing inputs and observing the output. It is then required to re-produce the function's behaviour, proving that it correctly determined what the function does.

In that paper, when we tried using a random heuristic to pick inputs, we found over-all better performance.

In this research note, we show that it is trivial to make a problem-set for which the opposite is true.

2 Experimental Setup

We will use OpenAI's o4-mini on "medium" reasoning settings. We use SherlockBench-Client release v1.2.0[1] thusly:

- 3-phase mode is used for LLM investigation
- random_inv mode is used for random investigation

3 Results

Here are the scores on the "Sherlock1" problem-set[2] used in the aforementioned paper:

Tested with 10 attempts per problem. We can see that in all cases, a random investigation is better.

Function	random	LLM
can form triangle	100	100
count consonants	100	100
even sum	100	100
sandwich letters	100	100
ignore two args	100	90
add biggest and smallest	100	80
subtract half	90	70
all odd or even	80	60
difference of closest pair	100	40
odd length reverse	100	40
set heading	0	0
crack lock	0	0

And here for our new "Mycroft1" problem-set[3]:

Tested with 10 attempts per problem. We can see that in all cases but two, the LLM's investigation is better.

Function	random	LLM
fizzbuzz with different words	80	100
count identical	60	100
peak side	20	100
subtract number of unique values from fixed value	20	100
valley or mountain	0	70
is descending	60	30
multiple3, bigger	40	30
prime, even	10	30
crack lock	0	20
set heading	0	20

4 Bibliography

Software

- [1] Xylon2. *joseph-xylon/sherlockbench-client: SherlockBench Client*. Version v1.2.0. Aug. 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16723052. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16723052>.
- [2] Joseph Bruce Anthony Graham. *joseph-xylon/sherlockbench-problems-sherlock1: SherlockBench Sherlock1 Problem-Set*. Version v1.3.1. July 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15801057. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15801057>.
- [3] Xylon2. *joseph-xylon/sherlockbench-problems-mycroft1: SherlockBench Mycroft1 Problem-Set*. Version v1.0.1. Aug. 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16722900. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16722900>.

Articles

- [4] Joseph Bruce Anthony Graham. *SherlockBench, Where Large Language Models Under-Perform Random Heuristics*. July 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16270954. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16270954>.